

ELIXIR Commissioned Service: ELIXIR Training Platform 2024-2026

M4.2 A first version of the strategy and indicators to assess the impact

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

The ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer (TtT) programme is a capacity-building initiative within the ELIXIR Training Platform (Work Package 4) that develops bioinformatics trainers across European nodes. Unlike standard training, TtT has a multiplicative effect: each trained instructor subsequently delivers training to many learners, amplifying ELIXIR's overall impact on research capacity.

This document presents the first version of a strategy and set of indicators to assess the impact of the TtT programme (Milestone M4.2). The strategy is grounded in the New World Kirkpatrick Model, structured around four levels of evaluation: participant reaction (Level 1), learning outcomes (Level 2), on-the-job behaviour (Level 3), and organisational results (Level 4). This framework enables a backward-design approach, starting from the desired outcome—a sustainable, high-quality European training infrastructure—and identifying the behaviours, knowledge, and required drivers needed to achieve it.

The strategy builds on ELIXIR's existing Training Metrics Database (TMD) infrastructure and defines concrete, measurable indicators across all four Kirkpatrick levels. An action plan details six implementation steps: enhancing TtT-specific data collection in TMD, establishing an alumni tracking system, conducting qualitative impact case studies, strengthening organisational drivers for behaviour change, integrating TtT impact data into ELIXIR-wide reporting, and establishing a continuous improvement cycle. The strategy balances methodological rigour with practical feasibility, ensuring that evaluation findings actively inform programme development. This milestone document constitutes the foundation for the final impact assessment strategy to be delivered in D4.6 (A final strategy and set of measurable indicators to assess the impact of the TtT programme).

Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
IT-Italy	Italy - University of Rome "Sapienza"	Allegra, Via	0000-0002-339 8-5462
CH-Switzerland	Switzerland - SIB SWISS INSTITUTE OF BIOINFORMATICS	Patricia, Palagi	0000-0001-906 2-6303

Abbreviations and Acronyms

TtT	ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer
TMD	Training Metrics Database

Supporting Documents

The supporting document for M4.2 can be found at:

[A first version of the strategy and indicators to assess the impact](#)